

SECTION 2: MULTI-TOPICS 2022

D5.1: Quality and Safety of Agro-pastoral Products from Living Labs Pre-intervention

PAS-AGRO-PAS

The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism

Quality and Safety of Agro-pastoral Products from Living Labs Pre-intervention

1. Introduction

The Making of Fragile Agro-ecosystems Productive, Adaptive, and Sustainable: Multifunctional Agro-pastoralism project aims to enhance the resilience and sustainability of agro-pastoral systems. A key aspect of this project involves evaluating the quality and safety of agro-pastoral products from living labs before implementing any intervention measures. This deliverable focuses on presenting the quality of milk ie fatty acid (FA) profile of milk produced under conventional farming system applied in Cyprus which characterized by low grazing/forage participation in the diets (use of forage between 40 to 50% as the percentage of the total diet) in small ruminants. By analyzing the FA profiles, we aim to establish a baseline of the milk lipids produced, providing as well insights on the existing literature for potential improvements in product quality using agro-pastoral practices (high grazing or forage use).

2. Background

2.1. Agro-pastoral Systems

Agro-pastoral systems integrate agricultural and livestock production, playing a crucial role in rural livelihoods and sustainable land management. These systems are especially important in fragile ecosystems, where they enhance resilience to environmental stresses and contribute to food security. In those systems the feeding is based more on forages either as grazing or fed roughage material. By combining crop cultivation and animal husbandry, agro-pastoral systems optimize resource use, and improve possibly the quality of the products produced under agro-pastoral methods of animal husbandry respecting the feeding ethology.

2.2. Forage: Concentrate ratio in ruminant diets

As has been suggested by several researchers, the milk's FA profile is affected by the forage participation in the animal diets and FA is a key determinant of the nutritional quality and health benefits of the animal products. The FA present in milk can impact the end product (cheese, yogurt) and consequently various human health outcomes, such as cardiovascular health, inflammatory responses, and metabolic processes. Higher forage participation in the feed, such as those applied in organic farming or grass-fed systems may lead to different

FA profiles compared to intensive systems that use high concentrate participation in the rations, particularly in countries, such as Cyprus, with forage scarcity due to arid conditions. Indeed, with regards to studies comparing organic and conventional bovine milk derived from farms or retail outlets in Europe, a significantly higher concentration of PUFA was reported for organic milk (Średnicka-Tober et al., 2016; Ormston et al., 2023). A majority of studies also demonstrated a higher proportion of CLA content in organic milk, apart from Ellis et al. (2006) and Adler et al. (2013), who found no difference. It is worth noting that in the past decades, there is also growing interest of consumer need for organically produced milk and public's awareness on the diets used in ruminant production. The majority of fat in milk and milk product are in the form of saturated FA which have health risk regarding obesity or coronary heart disease (Bauman et al., 2006). Beside to this, there is also confirmation that milk from ruminant animals contain omega 3 polyunsaturated FA and conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) which has potential benefits for human health on prevention of metabolic diseases and cancer, anti-atherogenic and anti-obesity effects, and immune-system modulation (Basak et al., 2020). Today, feeding ruminants with a high-forage diet is becoming an attractive research area and it is proposed as a method to enhance the levels of health-promoting fatty acids in milk. Indeed, many recent studies evaluating the different forage to concentrate ratios in the FA profile in milk have shown beneficial effects, particularly when forage was used in high quantities. For example, Mierlita et al. (2022) observed that the decrease in the forage: concentrate ratio had a negative effect on omega-3 fatty acids of bovine milk. In this experiment, cows fed with high (65:35) or low (50:50) forage to concentrate ratios. Also, Angeles-Hernandez et al. (2020) reported that sheep fed high-concentrate diets (HC; concentrate content >40% DM), had lower milk CLA content compared to those fed high-forage diets (HF; forage content >40% DM). On the other hand, compared with high forage (70:30), feeding low (30:70) forage: concentrate ratio moderately decreased the biohydrogenation of 18:2n-6, leading to a higher level of polyunsaturated fatty acids in milk fat (Jaakamo et al., 2019).

In conclusion, altering the forage-to-concentrate ratios in ruminant diets suggests that the quality of the milk produced can be affected. In the current project, we aim to establish a baseline understanding of the effects of low forage/pasture diets on milk quality by analyzing the fatty acid profiles of milk from conventional farming systems in Cyprus. This research will provide insights for potential improvements in agro-pastoral practices.

2.3. Relevance to Project Goals

Assessing the impact of forage and pasture inclusion in ruminant diets on the fatty acid profile of milk is central to our project's goals of enhancing agro-ecosystem sustainability and farmer engagement. To achieve this, we will first analyze the fatty acid profiles of milk from ruminants fed a low-forage diet. This initial analysis will provide essential baseline data, which is crucial for understanding the current state before implementing any interventions. Following this, we will compare these profiles with those from ruminants on high-forage diets. This comparison will help us identify potential nutritional benefits and areas where conventional practices could be refined to improve milk quality. Finally, these insights will guide targeted interventions aimed at optimizing agro-pastoral practices, thereby increasing the sustainability, resilience, and overall appeal of these systems for farmers and the environment.

3. Methodology

3.1. Site Selection and sample collection

The study includes data from several selected conventional farms with low forage participation (40% diet inclusion in dry matter) that are representative of the country's sheep and goat dairy farming sector based on their annual milk yield. The data are presented as means from milk samples collected from Damascus goats (caprine) and cross-bred Chios ewes (ovine).

3.1.1. Milk Sample Handling

After their collection, the milk samples were stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to preserve their integrity until further analysis. The collected milk samples underwent a detailed analysis to determine their fatty acid profiles. The steps involved in the analysis were as follows.

3.1.2. Fatty Acid Extraction

Lipids from milk were extracted, as described by Tzamaloukas et al. (2015). Briefly, 1.5-mL aliquots of fresh milk were first centrifuged at $17,800\times\text{ g}$ for 30 min. at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The resulting separated fat globules (lipid cake) were removed, placed in new tubes, and then allowed to melt at room temperature for 20 min. The samples were then recentrifuged at $19,500\times\text{ g}$ for 20 min. at room temperature, and 20 mg aliquots of the resulting lipid cake

were removed to new tubes and dispersed in 1 mL of n-hexane by shaking. The extracted lipids were then trans-esterified to convert fatty acids into their methyl esters (FAMES).

3.1.3. Gas Chromatography (GC) Analysis

Fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) were prepared by transesterification with methanolic potassium hydroxide according to the ISO method (2000). The FAME profiles were generated using a GCMS-QP2010 Plus Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer (Shimadzu, Duisburg, Germany) that was equipped with a 50 m × 0.25 mm × 0.2 μm column (Agilent CP-Sil 88 fused- silica capillary column) with a split ratio of 1:20. The column was held for 1 min. at 80 °C after injection, increased at 20 °C/min. to 120 °C, then raised to 193 °C at 1 °C/min., and finally increased to 220 °C at 5 °C/min. Helium was the carrier gas at 1 mL/min., with both injector and inter-face temperatures of 225 °C. Chromatographic profiles were analyzed using Shimadzu GCMS Postrun Solution software (GCMSsolution, Shimadzu, Duisburg, Germany). Individual peaks were identified by comparison of their retention indices and mass spectra to those of commercially available standards (Supelco 37-FAME standard mix, CLA cis-9, trans-11, CLA trans-10, cis-12, C18:1 trans-11; Sigma-Aldrich, Gillingham, UK) and mass spectral libraries (NIST) quantitated by peak integration and expressed as a percentage of the total fat.

4. Results

Table 1. Effect of low forage farming system on the fatty acid composition (expressed as a percentage of total fatty acid methyl esters) of caprine milk.

PARAMETER	LOW FORAGE PARTICIPATION
Saturated Fatty Acids	68,33
Monounsaturated Fatty Acids	25,66
Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids	4,88
Atherogenic index ¹	2,17

¹ Atherogenic index = $(C12:0 + 4 \times C14:0 + C16:0)/(MUFA + PUFA)$

Table 2. Effect of low forage farming system on the fatty acid composition (expressed as a percentage of total fatty acid methyl esters) of ovine milk.

PARAMETER	LOW FORAGE PARTICIPATION
Saturated Fatty Acids	71,06
Monounsaturated Fatty Acids	23,14
Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids	4,03
Atherogenic index ¹	2,98

¹ Atherogenic index = $(C12:0 + 4 \times C14:0 + C16:0)/(MUFA + PUFA)$

5. Discussion

The presence of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) in animal-origin products has beneficial effects on human health. This benefit can be achieved by including high-forage diets in animal feeding (Mollica et al., 2021). Indeed, according to results that are found in UK dairy farms with cows, the milk that originated from high forage production systems has an increased nutritionally desirable PUFA content, i.e., RA, ALA, eicosapentaenoic, and docosapentaenoic acids, and reduced the levels of the undesirable palmitic acid (Stergiadis et al., 2019). Indeed, results from this UK studies indicate that milk from high-forage production systems has increased levels of nutritionally desirable polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), such as rumenic acid (RA), alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), eicosapentaenoic acid, and docosapentaenoic acid, while showing reduced levels of the undesirable palmitic acid (Stergiadis et al., 2019). Given that leafy pasture plants are rich in n-3 fatty acids, their consumption leads to increased n-3 PUFA content in milk (Butler et al., 2020). However, several factors influence the rate and extent of ruminal biohydrogenation of PUFAs. Feeding ruminants diets high in PUFAs can inhibit the final phase of the biohydrogenation process in the rumen. As a result, there is a higher concentration of intermediate FA, which are then more likely to flow into the small intestine, where they are absorbed and transported to the mammary gland, ultimately being excreted in the milk (Sun and Gibbs, 2012). However, according to Halmemies-Beauchet-Filleau et al. (2013), the mechanisms underlying the high PUFA levels in milk from cows are not well defined. It has been postulated that factors such as high polyphenol oxidase activity, decreased lipolysis in the rumen, and changes in digestion kinetics, feed particle size, and rumen bacterial composition may contribute to higher ruminal escape of PUFAs.

The concentrations of total monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) in milk can be influenced by altering the forage-to-concentrate ratio in animals' diets. More specific, increasing the forage: concentrate ratio has been shown to decrease the total MUFA content in cow's milk, as reported by Vazirigohar et al. (2013). The composition and quantity of concentrates in the diet impact the extent of lipolysis and biohydrogenation processes occurring in the rumen (Palmquist et al., 2005). This influence is partly attributed to the decrease in rumen pH and the subsequent alterations in microbial communities caused by higher concentrate supplementation (Fuentes et al., 2009; Weimer et al., 2010). Additionally, changing the forage-to-concentrate ratio affects the complete biohydrogenation of 18-carbon unsaturated fatty acids to stearic acid (18:0) in the rumen,

leading to changes in the relative abundance of specific trans isomers leaving the rumen and incorporated into milk fat (Shingfield and Griinari, 2007). Furthermore, the effects of changes in Forage: Concentrate ratio on milk 18:1 composition also differ, depending on the presence or absence of plant oils in the basal diet (Vazirigochar et al., 2013).

It is generally known that saturated fatty acids in ruminant milk account for 60% to 70% of fatty acids. The main SFA in milk fat of the majority of mammals is C16:0, while a higher concentration of C6:0, C8:0, and C10:0 fatty acids in sheep and goat milk in comparison to cow's milk cause a specific aroma in milk of these little ruminants. The content of SFA could be decreased after the inclusion of high forage. This result is confirmed by Martini et al. (2010), who observed that a greater proportion of forage, compared with a higher percentage of concentrate, led to a decrease in the percentages of some medium chain FA (C12:0, C14:0; -14.89% and -4.03 respectively) when Massese ewes receiving diets with different forage:concentrate ratios and specifically, two different forage: concentrate ratios (60:40 and 40:60). High intake of starch is associated with a higher level of *de novo* synthesis resulting in more saturated milk fat (Kalač & Samková, 2010).

6. Conclusion

Our pre-intervention study presents the fatty acid profile of milk from small ruminants under conventional feeding strategies typically used in Cyprus. We hypothesize that including high forage in ruminants' diets could positively influence the fatty acid profile of milk by reducing saturated fatty acid (SFA) levels and increasing beneficial polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs). These results support the practice of pasture grazing and high forage inclusion in farming systems to enhance milk quality. Future research should investigate various forage-to-concentrate ratios, specific feed components, plant species, and management practices to further optimize the fatty acid profile of milk."

7. References

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